

Generation of enteroids from frozen porcine jejunum

Note: for the reagents refer to “List of reagents for enteroid protocols” (DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13847508)

- 1) Quickly thaw cryovials containing pieces of frozen jejunum in a 37°C water bath
- 2) Wash pieces of intestine twice with ice-cold PBSL containing 5% FBS
- 3) Incubate pieces in decontamination medium (PBSL+pennicillin, streptomycin and fungizone) for 20' on ice on a rocking platform

For the crypt isolation proceed with steps 11-25 of the protocol “Generation of enteroids from fresh porcine jejunum” (DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13848853)